

**DIGITAL SILENCE: HOW LACK OF FEEDBACK AFFECTS ONLINE
STUDENT MOTIVATION**

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Annotation: This article investigates a big problem of online learning- digital silence. Digital silence occurs when students don't get answers or feedback from their teachers or classmates. The article explains the importance of feedback as it helps students do better in school, feel more confident to stay interested in learning.

Also, the article explores key causes of digital silence in online learning, including teacher workload, technological challenges, low student confidence, and limited group interaction. Consequences include reduced engagement, feelings of isolation, and course withdrawal. Proposed solutions involve timely and supportive feedback, increased group work, professional development for online teaching, and the use of digital tools such as chatbots and online forums. The aim is to foster a more interactive, engaging, and inclusive virtual learning environment.

Keywords: digital silence, feedback, online learning, student motivation, peer interaction, teacher engagement, communication barriers, learning tools, educational technology, student participation

**ЦИФРОВОЕ МОЛЧАНИЕ: КАК ОТСУТСТВИЕ ОБРАТНОЙ
СВЯЗИ ВЛИЯЕТ НА МОТИВАЦИЮ СТУДЕНТОВ В ОНЛАЙН-
ОБУЧЕНИИ**

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Аннотация: Статья исследует проблему цифрового молчания в онлайн-обучении, возникающего при отсутствии обратной связи от преподавателей или однокурсников. Отмечается важность своевременной поддержки, способствующей успеваемости и мотивации студентов. Среди причин цифрового молчания выделяются перегрузка преподавателей, технические сложности, низкая уверенность учащихся и дефицит группового взаимодействия. Последствия включают снижение вовлечённости, изоляцию и отказ от обучения. В качестве решений предлагаются оперативная обратная связь, развитие групповой работы, повышение квалификации преподавателей и использование цифровых инструментов (чат-ботов, форумов). Цель — создание активной и инклюзивной онлайн-среды.

Ключевые слова: цифровое молчание, обратная связь/ комментарий, онлайн-обучение, мотивация студентов, взаимодействие между учениками, вовлечённость преподавателя, барьеры в общении, инструменты обучения, образовательные технологии, участие студентов

**RAQAMLI SUKUT: MULOHAZA YO‘QLIGI ONLAYN TA’LIMDAGI
TALABALAR MOTIVATSIYASIGA QANDAY
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Annotatsiya: Maqola onlayn ta’limdagi muhim muammo — raqamli sukunatni tahlil qiladi. Raqamli sukunat bu — o‘quvchilarning o‘qituvchilar yoki tengdoshlaridan javob va fikr ololmasligi holatidir. Maqolada fikr-mulohaza (feedback) o‘quvchilarni o‘qishga qiziqtirish va ularning ishonchini oshirishda muhim omil ekani ta’kidlanadi. Raqamli sukunatning asosiy sabablari sifatida o‘qituvchilarning ish yuklamasi, texnik muammolar, o‘quvchilarning o‘ziga ishonchsizligi va guruh ishlarining yetishmasligi ko‘rsatilgan. Natijada, ishtirok pasayadi, yolg‘izlik hissi ortadi va o‘quvchilar kursni tark etadi. Muammoni bartaraf etish uchun maqolada o‘z vaqtida va qo‘llab-quvvatlovchi fikr-mulohaza, guruh ishlarini kengaytirish, o‘qituvchilarni onlayn ta’limga tayyorlash va chat-botlar, forumlar kabi raqamli vositalardan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi. Maqsad — interaktiv, jalb qiluvchi va inklyuziv onlayn muhit yaratishdir.

Kalit so‘zlar: raqamli sukunat, fikr-mulohaza/ izoh (feedback), onlayn ta’lim, talaba motivatsiyasi, o‘quvchilararo muloqot, o‘qituvchining faol ishtiroki, aloqa to‘siqlari, o‘quv vositalari, ta’lim texnologiyalari, talabalarning ishtiroki.

Introduction

Nowadays, many students study on the internet. Online learning is becoming more and more popular. But sometimes, online classes feel too quiet. This quiet feeling is called digital silence. It happens when students don’t get answers to their

questions or comments from teachers. In a normal classroom, teachers and students talk, ask questions, and share ideas. But in online classes, this often doesn't happen.

Feedback is very important in learning. When teachers give feedback, they help students understand what they are doing right and what needs to be better. It also shows students that the teacher cares about them. This can make students feel more excited and confident about learning. But if there is no feedback, students might feel confused, unimportant, or alone.

After COVID-19, many schools started using online classes. This helped students continue learning at home. But it also brought new problems. One big problem is that students don't get enough feedback. Because of this, they may feel bored and stop trying their best.

This paper will talk about how not getting feedback in online classes can hurt student motivation. It will explain why feedback is needed, how students feel when they don't get it, and what teachers can do to help. The goal is to make online learning better and more active for students.

The Role of Feedback in Student Motivation

Feedback is a very important part of learning. It shows students if they are doing something well or if they need to change something. Good feedback can help students feel surer of themselves and more interested in learning. Without it, students may feel confused and think their work doesn't matter.

Some experts have explained why feedback helps with motivation. For example, Self-Determination Theory says people are more motivated when they feel supported, strong, and in control. Feedback shows students that someone cares about their learning. This gives them more energy to keep going. Another idea called Behaviorism says people learn better when they get rewards or corrections. Feedback works like a reward or a message to do something differently.

Feedback helps students become better. When they know what is good and what needs more work, they can improve. It also helps them feel proud because they

know they are learning well. This makes them want to keep trying. But students who don't get feedback often feel unsure. They don't know if their answers are right or wrong.

There are many types of feedback. Positive feedback tells students what they did well. This makes them feel happy and encouraged. Negative feedback shows mistakes, but if it is kind, it helps students learn and do better next time. But if there is no feedback at all, students feel invisible. They may stop caring about their learning.

In short, feedback helps students stay motivated. Whether it is good or pointing out mistakes, it must be useful and respectful. But if there is no feedback, digital silence grows—and this stops students from learning well.

Causes and Examples of Digital Silence

Sometimes teachers have too much work or too many students. They don't have enough time to answer all questions or give feedback quickly. When students wait a long time, they feel forgotten. For example, a student may send a message about homework and wait for days without an answer. This makes the student feel sad and ignored.

In regular classrooms, students talk, ask questions, and work in groups. But in many online classes, students learn alone. They don't talk or connect with each other. This makes them feel lonely. For example, in a Zoom class, students may turn off their cameras and stay silent. No one knows who is listening or learning.

Technology can also cause silence. Some students have bad internet, broken devices, or don't know how to use online tools. Also, some students feel shy or nervous online. They are scared to make mistakes or look bad. Because of this, they don't ask questions even if they want to.

In one class, a student named Sara always did her homework, but the teacher never gave any feedback. After some time, she stopped working hard. She felt like no one cared. In another class, students were asked to talk in a group chat. But no

one replied because they were shy and didn't know each other. So, the teacher stopped the activity.

These examples show that digital silence is not just about being quiet. It has many causes—too much teacher work, no connection between students, tech problems, and feelings like fear or sadness. If we understand these reasons, we can make online classes more fun and active.

Effects of Digital Silence on Learners

Digital silence can hurt students a lot. When there is no talk or feedback in online classes, many students feel confused, sad, or lose interest in learning.

When students do not hear from teachers or classmates, they feel alone. They may think nobody sees their work or cares about them. For example, if a student writes in a group chat and no one replies, they feel ignored. This can make them feel like they don't belong in the class.

When students feel like no one is listening, they stop trying. They may stop asking questions, doing activities, or speaking in class. For example, a student who never gets feedback from the teacher may stop writing or even stop coming to class. Without support, students lose their love for learning.

Feedback helps students feel proud of their work and get better. But when they don't get it, they don't know if they are doing well or badly. Their marks may get worse. They may start thinking they are not smart. Their self-confidence becomes low, and they stop believing in themselves.

If students keep feeling invisible, they may stop learning. Some students might drop the course. Others may stop turning on their cameras, skip homework, or stop listening. Once they lose interest, it is hard to get them back.

In short, digital silence is not just a quiet class. It hurts students' hearts and minds. It makes them feel alone, stops their progress, and takes them away from learning. That is why communication and feedback are so important in online education.

Solutions and Recommendations

Digital silence can make online learning hard, but we can fix it. Teachers, students, and schools can all work together to make online classes better and more active.

1. Using technology tools to reduce silence: Discussion forums where students and teachers can ask and answer any time. AI chatbots that give fast answers to student questions. Polls and surveys to know how students feel. Video messages from teachers that feel warm and personal

2. Give clear rules and instructions: Tell students clearly what they need to do and how to talk in online classes. This helps them know what is expected and feel more confident to join in.

3. Use fun and active ideas: Try different ways to get students involved—like group chats, quick polls, or working together on a project. These tools can help make online classes more exciting.

4. Give feedback often: Teachers should check students' work and tell them how they are doing. Quick and regular feedback helps students know what they do well and what to improve.

5. Make a friendly class online: Help students feel welcome and part of the group. When students talk to each other and feel safe, they are more likely to join and enjoy the class.

6. Notice quiet students too: Some students do not talk in class, but they are still learning. This is called "lurking." Teachers should understand this but also try to help quiet students join more by giving them support and asking for small actions like writing a comment.

7. Write helpful notes: When checking homework or online posts, give clear and kind comments that help students know what is good and what to change.

8. Send video messages: Teachers can record short videos to give personal feedback. Students like hearing the teacher's voice—it feels warmer and more caring.

9. Talk while students work: Use shared documents or tools like Google Docs to give help and feedback while students are working. This way, students get answers fast.

10. Let students help each other: Ask students to read and comment on each other's work. This peer feedback builds teamwork and helps them learn from one another.

11. Help students check themselves: Teach students to use simple tools like checklists to see how they are doing. Self-checking helps them feel more in control of their learning.

Conclusion

Today, digital silence is a real problem in online classes. When students do not get feedback or support, they feel alone, lost, and unmotivated. This can lead to less learning and sometimes dropping out. Feedback is not just about marks. It helps students learn, feel seen, and stay part of the class. To stop digital silence, teachers, schools, and online platforms must work together. They should give regular feedback, create friendly class spaces, and use smart tools to help students and teachers talk more. With these steps, online learning can become more active, caring, and successful for all.

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